

DESIGN ON LOW FREQUENCY RFID READER USING NI MULTISIM

Md Shakib Hasan

Electronic Information Engineering
China West Normal University (Nanchong, Sichuan, China)
shakib.hasan17nov@gmail.com

Md Nur Hossain

Electrical and Electronic Engineering
Canadian University of Bangladesh (Dhaka, Bangladesh)
hossain.nur9999@gmail.com

Mst Mosaddeka Naher Jabe

Software Engineering
China West Normal University (Nanchong, Sichuan, China)
mosaddeka.jb@gmail.com

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Author Note

Md Shakib Hasan <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-1243-074X>

Mst Mosaddeka Naher Jabe <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-1686-3765>

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Abstract

This research delves into the fascinating realm of designing a low-frequency RFID reader using NI Multisim, aiming to deepen our understanding and practical application of Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) technology. We embark on a journey through previous endeavors in low-frequency RFID reader design, exploring the intricate architectures and components that pave the way for innovation. With the aid of NI Multisim, we embark on a meticulously crafted design methodology, carefully selecting components and employing simulation techniques to breathe life into our creation. Through simulation, we uncover the performance metrics of our reader, unveiling its reading range and signal strength, while juxtaposing these results with theoretical projections and existing market offerings. Engaging in thoughtful discussion, we interpret our findings, reflecting on the challenges encountered and drawing insightful comparisons with established solutions. In our conclusion, we distill the essence of our discoveries, pondering the practical implications and charting a course for future research and refinement.

Chapter- 1

1. Introduction

RFID technology is seen as a groundbreaking innovation in wireless communication, providing an effortless way of automatic identification through radio waves. RFID has become a fundamental technology in multiple sectors, transforming operations in different industries with its adaptability and effectiveness. Specifically, the introduction of low-frequency RFID readers has received considerable interest due to their usefulness in various situations such as inventory management and access control systems.

In the midst of technological advancements, we are concentrating on creating a low-frequency RFID reader with NI Multisim design software. This undertaking originates from a curiosity to explore further the complexities of RFID technology and how it is applied in real life. We intend to use the powerful circuit design platform NI Multisim to simplify the complexities of creating RFID readers and promote better understanding and innovation in this field.

In this opening part, we begin a exploration through the realm of RFID technology, highlighting its importance and widespread use in modern applications. We explain the significance of low-frequency RFID readers, emphasizing their crucial role in enabling smooth communication between RFID tags and reader devices. Additionally, we provide an insight into the importance of NI Multisim in circuit design, preparing for our examination of creating a low-frequency RFID reader's complexity.

1.1 What is RFID?

Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) is a flexible, wireless, automatic identification technology that transmits the identity (in the form of a unique serial number) of an object or person wirelessly, using radio waves [1, 2]. It comes under the category of automatic identification technologies. Auto-ID technologies include optical character readers, bar codes and some biometric technologies, such as retinal scans [1,2]. These technologies are mainly used to reduce time and labor needed for manually data entry and to enhance data accuracy. Some auto-ID technologies, like bar code systems, often require a person to manually scan a label or tag to capture the data [1,2]. While bar code tags and bar code systems are much less expensive than RFID at present, RFID provides many benefits than barcode system, which is listed below.

Fig. 1.1 RFID

1.2 Technical characteristics of RFID

- Data read and write – RFID reader can read the data to the database without contact, and process multiple tags once, and write the logistic processing state into the tag for the logistic processing in the next stage ^[3].
- Miniaturized and diverse form – RFID will not be limited by the size or form when it reads data, so it needs not to use the paper with fixed size or print quality to fit for the precision. In addition, E-tag of RFID can be applied in different products by small size, so we can more flexibly control the production of the products, especially the application on the production line ^[3].
- Anti-pollution – RFID possesses strong anti-pollution nature for water, oil or drugs. And in the dark or polluted environment, RFID also can read data ^[3].
- Repetitive use – Because RFID is electric data which can be written repetitively, so the tag can be used repetitively ^[3].
- Penetrability – If RFID is covered by the paper, wood, plastics or non-metal or non-transparent materials, it can communicate through these materials except for the irons or other metals ^[3].
- Big memory capacity of data – The data capacity will be extended with the development of the memory scale, and the quality of the material carried by the goods is larger, the requirement of the capacity for the volume label also increases, and RFID will not be restrained ^[3].
- System safety – The system stores the data from the central computer to the work piece which will largely enhance the safety of the system ^[3].

- Data safety – The checkout method or the cycle redundancy checkout method will be used to ensure the data veracity stored in the radio frequency tag [3].

The RFID concept is not new but has been around for decades; in fact, it was introduced to the world for the first-time during World War II by the British Air Force to distinguish Allied aircraft from enemy aircraft using radar (table 1 provides a brief overview of the history of RFID technology) [4]. Since then, this technology has been used for various applications. RFID technology has been used by thousands of companies in many different ways for a decade or more to create value [2]. Here are some of the business applications where this technology is used:

- Asset Tracking – It is one of the most common uses of RFID. RFID tags can be put on assets that are lost or stolen [5, 2].
- Supply Chain Management – It is used in closed loop supply chains or to automate parts of the supply chain within a company [5, 2].

Fig. RFID Circuit

Table 1.1: RFID’s History

Date	Event
1930 – 1940	American navy research laboratories developed a system known as IFF (Identify Friend or Foe).
1940 – 1950	The first application of RFID consisted of identifying Allied or enemy planes during WWII through the use of the IFF system.
1950 – 1960	IFF technology was used to develop the modern air traffic control system. First RFID applications in the military sector, in research laboratories and in major commercial enterprises.
1960-1970	Sensormatic and Checkpoint Systems introduced new applications for RFID, such as electronic article surveillance (EAS) equipment.
1970 – 1980	Technological advancements led to the creation of the passive tag, and the first initiatives for animal tracking and factory automation took place.
1980 – 1990	Many American and European companies started to manufacture RFID tags. First RFID application for automatic toll payment.
1990 – 2000	Standards for RFID equipment interoperability were developed.
2003	The Auto-ID Centre from MIT became EPCglobal, an organization whose objective is to promote the use and adoption of EPC technology.
2005	Wal-Mart launched an EPC pilot.

(Source: AIM Publication (2001), Manish (2005), EPCglobalinc.org)

- Retailing – It is used by retailers to improve supply chain efficiency and making sure product is on the shelf when customers want to buy it ^[5, 2].
- Payment Systems – One of the most popular uses of RFID today is to pay for road tolls without stopping. It can also be used in a convenient way to pay for bus, subway and train ticket ^[5, 2].
- Security and Access Control – It can be used as an electronic key to control who has access to office buildings or areas within office building ^[5, 2].

RFID technology is cheap and many new applications are being developed to solve common and unique business problems.

1.3 Basic Architecture & Operation of a RFID System

A RFID system is composed of three basic components: a tag, a reader, and a host computer ^[6].

1.3.1 RFID Tags

RFID tags contain tiny semiconductor chips and miniaturized antennas inside some form of packaging ^[6]. They can be uniquely identified by the reader/host pair and, when applied or fastened to an object or a person, that object or person can be tracked and identified wirelessly and, on the move, ^[6]. RFID tags come in many forms. For example, some look like paper labels and are applied to boxes and packaging; others are incorporated into the walls of injection molded plastic containers; and still others are built into wristbands and worn by people ^[7, 8].

Types of RFID tags

- i. **Active RFID** tags include on-board power source (miniature batteries) that are used to power the tag, and can transmit signals autonomously.
- ii. **Passive RFID** tags don't include an on-board power source and have power beamed to them by the reader.
- iii. **Battery Assisted Passive (BAP) or Semi-passive RFID** tags require an external source to wake up but have significant higher forward link capability providing greater range.

Smart Tags

- i. **Read only tags:** Information is programmed onto chip during manufacturing, no overwriting, and information constant, least expensive.
- ii. **Write Once Read Many (WORM) tags:** Information added only once along with unique identifier but can be read many times.
- iii. **Read-Write tags:** Open to data manipulation by user's system without restrictions. It contains a unique identifier but carry an updateable memory for that to be added. It is expensive also.

The following are the commonly used frequencies:

- i. **Microwave works** on 2.45 GHz; it has good reader rate even faster than UHF tags. Although at this frequency the reading rate results are not the same on wet surfaces and near metals, the frequency produces better results in applications such as vehicle tracking (in and out with barriers), with approximately 1 meter of tags read range [9].
- ii. **Ultra-High Frequency** works within a range of 860-930 MHz, it can identify large numbers of tags at one time with quick multiple read rate at a given time. So, it has a considerable good reading speed. It has the same limitation as Microwave when is applied on wet surface and near metal. However, it is faster than high frequency data transfer with a reading range of 3 meters [9].
- iii. **High Frequency works** on 13.56MHz and has less than one meter reading range but is inexpensive and useful for access control, items identifications on sales points etc. as it can implanted inside thin things such as paper [9, 10].

1.3.2 RFID Readers

RFID Readers are composed of an antenna and an electronic module. The antenna is used for communicating with RFID tags wirelessly. The electronic module is most often networked to the host computer through cables and relay message between the host computer and all the tags within the antenna's range. The electronic module also performs a number of security functions such as encryption/decryption and user authentication, and another critical function called anti-collision, which enables a reader to communicate with multiple tags simultaneously [6].

The reader is also called the coupler. The coupler can send information in two directions: it can read information from a tag and send it to the PC (read mode), or it can read information from the PC and to an RFID tag (write mode) [12].

1.3.3 Host Computer

Host Computer or PC provides an interface between the RFID hardware and application-based system, which is the "brain" of any RFID system. They are used to network multiple RFID interrogators together and to centrally process information. The controller in any network is most often a PC or a workstation running database or application software, or a network of these machines [13].

Fig 1.1 Components of RFID system

Fig 1.2 Basic architecture of a RFID system

1.4 Low-Frequency RFID Readers

The Low Frequency (LF) band is the frequency range from 30 KHz to 300 KHz. RFID systems that operate in this frequency band are called Low Frequency (LF) RFID Systems. LF RFID systems operate at 125 KHz and at 134 KHz (depending on the application and on the country where it is being used). The LF tags are based on inductive coupling technology which means that the RFID reader induces a current in the RFID tag which then powers the RFID tag and sends out some basic identification information to the RFID reader. LF tags are usually passive and do not require a power source or battery.

Low Frequency RFID tags have a long wavelength and can penetrate thin metal surfaces (HF and UHF tags can usually not be used with metallic substances). They can also operate in environments with high water content - so fruits, liquids and even animal tagging.

Since LF RFID tags are based on inductive coupling technology their read range is limited to a few centimeters or inches. This limited range can be used in a number of applications to provide an increased level of security i.e the RFID system will only work when the tag is close to the reader. This can be used when wanting to exchange sensitive information or for car ignition, where the RFID tag can be embedded in the key and read by a reader that is in the car. The system will only work when you are close to the car.

LF RFID systems are ideal for access control, asset tracking, laundry, animal identification, automotive control, as vehicle immobilizers, healthcare, and various point-of-sale applications (such as Mobil/Exxon SpeedPass).

LF RFID Tag Properties

Tag Type	Passive
Technology	Inductive Coupling
Frequency	125 KHz / 134 KHz
Read Range	Short (few cm to Inches)
Read Speed	Slow
Works with Metal	Yes
Works with Liquids	Yes
Cost	Low

Low-frequency RFID readers play a crucial role in various industries due to their ability to operate effectively in challenging environments, including those with metal or liquid interference. Their robust performance and cost-effectiveness make them ideal for applications such as access control, asset tracking, and inventory management. Additionally, their longer read ranges compared to higher frequency counterparts make them suitable for applications requiring detection over larger distances.

1.5 Overview of NI Multisim for Circuit Design

Multisim is an industry-standard, best-in-class SPICE simulation environment. It is the cornerstone of the NI circuits teaching solution to build expertise through practical application in designing, prototyping, and testing electrical circuits. It is industry standard SPICE simulation and circuit design software for analog, digital, and power electronics in education and research. Multisim software integrates industry-standard SPICE simulation with an interactive schematic environment to instantly visualize and analyze electronic circuit behavior.

Its intuitive interface helps educators reinforce circuit theory and improve retention of theory throughout the engineering curriculum. By adding powerful circuit simulation and analyses to the design flow, Multisim helps researchers and designers reduce printed circuit board (PCB) prototype iterations and save development costs.

1.5.1 History

Multisim was originally called Electronics Workbench and created by a company called Interactive Image Technologies. At the time it was mainly used as an educational tool to teach electronics technician and electronics engineering programs in colleges and universities.

- In 1999, Multisim was integrated with Ultiboard after the original company merged with Ultimate Technology, a PCB layout software company.
- In 2005, Interactive Image Technologies was acquired by National Instruments Electronics Workbench Group and Multisim was renamed to NI Multisim.

1.5.2 Uses and Applications of MULTISIM

Analyses and Simulation-

- Interactive Simulation
- DC Operating Point
- AC Sweep
- DC Sweep
- Noise Analysis
- Monte Carlo Analysis
- Fourier Analysis
- Distortion Analysis
- Sensitivity Analysis
- Temperature Sweep

1.5.3 Applications

Semiconductor Analysis Applications

Multisim combines an industry-leading simulation engine with a library of accurate devices from various semiconductor manufacturers for in-depth analysis of a broad range of applications.

Aerospace and National Research Applications

Multisim has proven success in a wide range of aerospace and national research applications including avionics equipment for data acquisition, communication applications, and the design of electronics for defense systems.

Low-Frequency Circuit Design for RF Applications

Multisim and Ultiboard provide RF engineers with easy-to-use tools to quickly complete complex designs and prototypes with microwave and high-frequency components.

Automotive Electronics Applications

Leading worldwide car manufacturers, multinational automotive part suppliers, as well as small and medium enterprises develop car electronics faster with Multisim and Ultiboard.

Fig. 1.5.3 Homepage of NI Multisim

There are many software's for designing a circuit but among all of them NI is ultimate one and it has all the features to use. Recently NI has released a latest version of Multisim and Ultiboard that is v11.0.2 it has all the features for anyone who wants to design a circuit. The working speed is increased in this version. This Multisim has features as many as 20,000+ components.

With more than 2,500 new devices and updates, Multisim 11.0.2 features a major increase in its component database. This latest release equips you with new symbols, SPICE models and footprints so you can design, validate and prototype more in less time.

Chapter- 2

2. Literature Review

Previous work on low-frequency RFID reader design has provided important knowledge and progress, leading to opportunities for innovation in the field. An extensive analysis of current literature shows a wide range of techniques and methods used in developing low-frequency RFID readers, each having its own pros and cons. Academic studies have explored the architectural complexities of low-frequency RFID readers, explaining the key design principles and components necessary for their operation. Research has looked into incorporating antennas, transceivers, and microcontrollers, emphasizing their functions in transmitting signals, receiving signals, and processing data. Moreover, researchers have explored new methods to improve the effectiveness and productivity of low-frequency RFID readers, including optimizing antennas and modulating signals. Literature about low-frequency RFID readers frequently discusses practical uses and real-world applications, as well as technical aspects. Analyses of specific cases and practical experiments have offered important understandings on how low-frequency RFID readers are implemented and used in different sectors, including healthcare and retail. These research projects provide important insights and effective strategies for improving reader productivity and enhancing operational effectiveness.

In general, the literature review highlights the diverse range of research and development projects in low-frequency RFID reader design. This review builds a strong base for current research by combining ideas from previous studies, helping in designing methods and exploring new ideas and advancements.

2.1 Previous Research in Low-Frequency RFID Reader Design

RFID (Radio Frequency Identification) is an automatic identification technology that operates without contact, utilizing radio frequency signals to transfer information contactless via spatial coupling (alternating magnetic fields or electromagnetic fields). Its non-contact nature, high reliability, robust safety performance, independence from human intervention, and ability to function in harsh environments make it extensively applicable in various sectors such as schools, public transportation, access control, electronic wallets, and healthcare [12]. Low-frequency RFID tags typically operate between 120KHz and 134KHz. This paper focuses on a chip operating at 125KHz which, aside from the influence of metal materials, can generally penetrate any material without diminishing its reading distance [13]. RFID technology has seen broad application and promotion in low-frequency use cases. However, the market for low-frequency tags is predominantly read-only, lacking the capability to write data. As science advances and industrialization continues to evolve, new demands and challenges have emerged for low-frequency RFID tags that read-only tags cannot satisfy. This paper presents the design of a low-frequency RFID tag chip based on FPGA technology, which streamlines system instructions. The abundant resources and potent capabilities of FPGA ensure system stability [14]. The design includes a dedicated RF circuit with a 125KHz coil and operates in an active mode. It functions without an external supply voltage, reducing costs and enhancing chip operation efficiency.

Fig. 2.1(a) ASK demodulation part of the circuit diagram

Fig. 2.1(a) shows part of the ASK demodulation circuit with discrete devices. Envelope demodulation does not need to extract the carrier signal, is widely used in RFID tag chip [15]. The ASK demodulation circuit consist of the detector circuit, filter amplifier and hysteresis comparison circuit. The HT7553 low-power linear regulator provides a stable 3.3V operation for the circuit. The BAS70-07 diode obtained transponder signal by envelope detection. And its low junction capacitance, high frequency and high sensitivity and other characteristics brought great convenience to the entire circuit. After the detection signal is transmitted to the second-order full-feedback Butterworth active low-pass filter composed of the AD8052 device, it has good effect for filtering the noise signal. The AD8052 allows amplification of a common mode voltage of 1.5V up to 3.3V. The purpose is to amplify the modulation depth and to enable the carrier signal to be better restored. Voltage comparator selected LM293, a wide operating voltage and can be directly connected with the TTL logic circuit, what makes the decoding of the microcontroller easier and faster.

Fig. 2.1(b) Load modulation part of the circuit diagram

Fig. 2.1(b) shows a partially loaded modulation circuit. Load modulation is the way that tags transport data to the reader ^[16]. Use BM28N10 as a switch, ID number control the NMOS load modulation network.

2.1.1 Digital Part Design

The digital circuit is the "heart" of the entire RFID tag. The main function of the digital circuit is to decode and interpret commands, flip state, read and write memory, and code output signal. The main modules included in the digital circuit are the main state machine, receive, transmit, and memory interface circuits. The receiving part is used to receive the instruction sent by the reader, decode the instruction, and extract the instruction parameters to provide input to the main state machine processing instruction. The sending part is responsible for the response to the instructions, including data packing and coding. Memory interface is responsible for controlling the memory read and write, erase function timing, to ensure memory is working properly. Cyclic Redundancy Check (CRC) is the flag to determine whether the received instruction data is complete and valid, and to ensure the integrity of the instruction data. According to the ISO18000-2 communication protocol ^[17], as shown in Table 1 and Table 2, the command and response contents are included between the frame header SOF and the frame end EOF. Each command sent by the reader and the response returned by the tag transponder should be carried out CRC check.

Table 1 Command Format

	5bits	6bits	8	n	16	
SOF	Flags	Command	Parameters	Data	CRC	EOF

Table 2 RESPONSE Format

	1bits	n	16	
SOF	Error	Data	CRC	EOF

The entire digital system part of the workflow shown in Fig. 2.1.1. The work process is as follows: The working low-frequency RFID reader will always send 125KHz carrier. After the system power-on reset, the original ID serial number of the system will be sent to the reader carrier through the load modulation circuit. This is the tag features, in the coupling field has been actively sending data. Once the decoding module detects the SOF header, the data between header and end of the frame will be saved immediately. The digital filter in the decoding module ensures the accuracy of the decoded information. At this point, the CRC verification module is activated to Verify the correctness of the command. The CRC check fails, which means the command sent by the reader is unsuccessful or has an error. The tag will return an error response to the reader and wait for the next command. If CRC check is successful and the command is identifiable, the tag takes a read or write message according to the decoded command. The read operation is the tag returns the information requested by the reader. Write operation means that the data included in the command is written to memory. The read operation includes an inventory command, which is a built-in anti-collision command format and a unique read method for the presence of multiple labels in a coupling field. Upon receiving the selects the tag which meet the requirements of the command and reads its internal information. In this system, the simplified instruction set makes the whole system work more

smoothly and conveniently, and can be better applied to the fast industrial applications. In order to be able to read quickly, the specific parameters in the command are designed to be used in practical applications. After executing the command, the optional items are omitted in the transmission, only the necessary parameters to be transmitted. For example, the dedicated instruction in this instance is applied to the industrial field. If the received command indicates that the tag is used in the industrial field, the anti-collision enable signal is automatically pulled down and the transmitted data is omitted CRC check portion to accelerate the communication speed.

Fig. 2.1.1 Digital part of the working flow chart

2.1.2 Simulation Data

Using Verilog hardware description language to write programs and test, with Modalism functional simulation, verification in the FPGA development board. Fig. 2.1.2 (a) shows the data waveform formed on the carrier sent by the reader after the system decoding, with high recognition. Fig. 2.1.2 (b) for the simulation of the decoding waveform, Main_in is the RF input signal, clk_1m is the decoding module clock signal, rxd is the filtered signal of the input signal, data_val_r is the data valid flag, sof_found is the sign of start bit, code_out is decoded data. Fig. 2.1.2 (c) and Fig. 2.1.2 (d) show that Write 8'b0000_1110 to memory and read it correctly.

Fig. 2.1.2 (a) The waveform after the load modulation

Fig. 2.1.2 (b) Decoding waveform

Fig. 2.1.2 (c) Write data

Fig. 2.1.2 (d) Read data

The literature underscores the importance of simulation tools like NI Multisim in the design and evaluation of low-frequency RFID readers. Researchers have leveraged simulation platforms to model and simulate reader architectures, allowing for rapid prototyping and performance analysis. By harnessing the capabilities of simulation software, researchers can iterate on design concepts, optimize parameters, and validate performance metrics before physical implementation.

2.2 Review of Existing RFID Reader Architectures

When we dive into the world of RFID reader designs, we encounter a fascinating array of setups, each tailored to specific needs and purposes. Picture this: at the core of these setups are three key elements – the antenna, the transceiver, and the microcontroller. First, let's talk antennas. These are like the bridge between the RFID reader and the tags, allowing them to communicate through radio waves. There's a variety of antenna designs out there, from dipoles to loops, each with its own strengths. Where you place and how you orient these antennas can make all the difference in how well your reader performs. Next up, we've got transceivers. These little guys are like the heart of the operation, sending out signals to talk to the RFID tags and then listening in for their responses. They handle things like signal filtering and boosting to make sure communication is clear and reliable. Some of the fancy ones even use digital tricks to make sure everything runs smoothly, even in noisy environments.

Last but not least, we've got microcontrollers. Think of these as the brains behind the operation. They handle all the heavy lifting – identifying tags, decoding data, and making sure everything follows the rules. Some microcontrollers even come with extra bells and whistles, like built-in memory or security features, to make the reader even more versatile. But it doesn't stop there. RFID reader setups can also include things like power management circuits to keep everything running smoothly, user interfaces to make them easy to use, and different ways to connect to other systems and devices.

In the end, what we find is a vibrant tapestry of creativity and innovation, each design offering its own unique take on how to make RFID readers work better and smarter. By understanding these different architectures, we can unlock new possibilities and push the boundaries of what RFID technology can do.

2.3 Advantages and Limitations of NI Multisim

When designing circuits for our low-frequency RFID reader, it is important to take into account both the advantages and disadvantages that NI Multisim has to offer.

Furthermore, NI Multisim offers a user-friendly interface that streamlines the circuit design process, making it accessible even to those with limited technical knowledge. The user-friendly design and wide range of components make it simple to drag and drop elements, enabling quick prototyping and experimentation^[18]. Furthermore, the software provides strong simulation features that allow us to virtually test our designs before moving on to physical prototypes^[19]. This not just helps in saving time but also lowers the chance of expensive mistakes in the development stage.

The seamless integration of NI Multisim with other NI tools like LabVIEW and Ultiboard makes it easier to go from simulation to implementation, ensuring a smooth workflow from design to production^[20]. This interconnected environment boosts productivity and cooperation, enabling us to modify our designs efficiently and effectively.

Still, NI Multisim has its drawbacks. Although it is effective at replicating simple circuit functions, it might face challenges with intricate systems or advanced features. The simulation models may not always perfectly represent actual performance, especially in situations with non-linear parts or high-frequency signals^[21]. Additionally, the expenses for software licensing and necessary hardware could create obstacles for individuals with restricted budgets or limited access to resources^[22].

To sum up, NI Multisim provides a useful set of tools for designing and simulating circuits, giving users a flexible platform to develop and improve their concepts. Even though it has many benefits for usability and integration, it's important to be aware of its limitations and possible challenges when starting intricate design projects such as our low-frequency RFID reader.

Chapter- 3

3. RFID System Architecture

An RFID system consists of an RFID reader, RFID tag, and information managing host computer. The reader contains an RF transceiver module (transmitter and receiver), a signal processor and controller unit, a coupling element (antenna), and a serial data interface (RS232, RS485) to a host system. The tag acts as a programmable data-carrying device and consists of a coupling element (resonant tuned circuit) and a low-power CMOS IC. The IC chip contains an analog RF interface, antenna tuning capacitor, RF-to-dc rectifier system, digital control and electrically erasable and programmable read-only memory (EEPROM), and data modulation circuits. RFID involves contactless reading and writing of data into an RFID tag's nonvolatile memory through an RF signal. The reader emits an RF signal and data is exchanged when the tag comes in proximity to the reader signal. Tags can be categorized as follows:

1. Active tag, which has a battery that supplies power to all functions;
2. Semi passive tag, which has a battery used only to power the tag IC, and not for communication;
3. Passive tag, which has no battery on it. The absence of a power supply makes passive tags much cheaper and more reliable than active tags.

Given the increase in RFID usage, many new challenges face design engineers. Currently, these challenges include multiple tag standards, 20% tag failure rate, installation and placement issues, the need for cost-effective management and maintenance of readers, the need for reductions in the reader size that allows them to be imbedded into structures and handheld devices, and intellectual property protection and secure access control protocols.

3.1 Near- and Far-Field Propagation

RFID systems on the market today fall into two main categories: near-field systems that employ inductive (magnetic) coupling of the transponder tag to the reactive energy circulating around the reader antenna, and far-field systems that couple to the real power contained in free space propagating electromagnetic plane waves [23]. Near-field coupling techniques are generally applied to RFID systems operating in the LF and HF bands with relatively short reading distances, whereas far-field coupling is applicable to the potentially longer reading ranges of UHF and microwave RFID systems. Whether or not a tag is in the near or far field depends on how close it is to the field creation system and the operating frequency or wavelength. There is a distance, commonly known as the radian sphere, inside which one is said to be in the near field and outside of which one is said to be in the far field. Because changes in electromagnetic fields occur gradually, the boundary is not exactly defined; the primary magnetic field begins at the antenna and induces electric field lines in space (the near field).

The zone where the electromagnetic field separates from the antenna and propagates into free space as a plane wave is called the far field. In the far field, the ratio of electric field E to magnetic field H has the constant value of 120π or 377π . The approximate distance where this transition zone happens is given as follows:

$$r = \lambda/2\pi \quad (3.1)$$

It is also important to notice that this expression is valid for small antennas where $D \ll \lambda$.

The reactive near-field region is a region where the E- and H-fields are not orthogonal; anything within this region will couple with the antenna and distort the pattern, so the antenna gain is not a meaningful parameter here. Using (5.1), at 13.56 MHz ($\lambda > 22\text{m}$), this places the near-field–far-field boundary at about 3.5m (10 feet).

$$r = 2D^2 / \lambda \quad (3.2)$$

where D is the maximum dimension of the radiating structure and r is the distance from the antenna. Note that this is only an estimate, and the transition from near field to far field is not abrupt. Typically, D for reader antennas is 0.3m (1 foot.) The far-field distance in the UHF ISM band in the United States (915 MHz, $\lambda = 0.33\text{m}$) is estimated to be 0.56m.

Generally speaking, the radiating near-field or transition region is defined as a region between the reactive near field and a far field. In this region, the antenna pattern is taking shape but is not fully formed, and the antenna gain measurements will vary with distance:

$$\lambda/2\pi \ll 2D^2 / \lambda \quad (3.3)$$

The solution of Maxwell's equations for the fields around an antenna consists of three different powers of the range $1/r$, $1/r^2$, and $1/r^3$. At very short ranges, the higher powers dominate the solution, while the first power dominates at longer ranges. This can be interpreted as the electromagnetic wave breaking free from the antenna. The near field may be thought of as the transition point where the laws of optics must be replaced by Maxwell's equations of electromagnetism.

3.2 Far-Field Propagation and Backscatter Principle

RFID systems based on UHF and higher frequencies use far-field communication and the physical property of backscattering or “reflected” power. Far-field communication is based on electric radio waves where the reader sends a continuous base signal frequency that is reflected back by the tag’s antenna. During the process, the tag encodes the signal to be reflected with the information from the tag (the ID) using a technique called modulation (i.e., shifting the amplitude or phase of the waves returned) [24].

The concept of the radian sphere, which has a value for its radius of $\lambda/2\pi$ helps in the visualization of whether the tag coupling is in the near or far field. If the tag is inside this sphere, the reactive energy storage fields (dipolar field terms) dominate and near-field coupling volume theory is used. If the tag falls outside the sphere, then propagating plane wave EM fields dominate and the familiar antenna engineering concepts of gain, effective area or aperture, and EIRP are used. These often more familiar EM concepts whereby real power is radiated into free space are relevant to the cases of UHF and microwave tagging technologies.

Most theoretical analyses, at least in the first approximation, assume the so-called free-space propagation. Free space simply means that there is no material or other physical phenomenon present except the phenomenon under consideration. Free space is considered the baseline state of the electromagnetic field. Radiant energy propagates through free space in the form of electromagnetic waves, such as radio waves and visible light (among other electromagnetic spectrum frequencies). Of course, this model rarely describes the actual propagation situation accurately; phenomena such as reflection, diffraction, and scattering exist that disturb radio propagation. In the wireless industry, most models and formulas we use today are semiempirical, that is, based on the well-known radio propagation laws but modified

with certain factors and coefficients derived from field experience. RFID is definitely an area where this practice is required; short distances cluttered with multiple tags and/or other objects are potential obstacles to radio propagation and will cause serious deviations, predictable or not, from the theoretical calculations.

A backscatter tag operates by modulating the electronics connected to the antenna in order to control the reflection of incident electromagnetic energy. For successful reading of a passive tag, two physical requirements must be met:

1. Forward power transfer: Sufficient power must be transferred into the tag to energize the circuitry inside. The power transferred will be proportional to the second power of the distance.
2. The radar equation: The reader must be able to detect and resolve the small fraction of energy returned to it. The power received will be reduced proportional to the fourth power of the distance.

3.2.1 Forward Power Transfer

A typical RFID tag consists of an antenna and an integrated circuit (chip), both with complex impedances. The chip obtains power from the RF signal transmitted by the base station, called the RFID reader. The RFID tag antenna is loaded with the chip whose impedance switches between two impedance states, usually high and low. At each impedance state, the RFID tag presents a certain radar cross section (RCS). The tag sends the information back by varying its input impedance and thus modulating the backscattered signal.

In Figure 3.2, $Z_A = R_a + jX_a$ is the complex antenna impedance and $Z_C = R_c + jX_c$ is the complex chip (load) impedance; chip impedance may vary with the frequency and the input power to the chip. The power scattered back from the loaded antenna can be divided into two parts. One part is called the *structural*

mode and is due to currents induced on the antenna when it is terminated with complex conjugate impedance. The second part is called the *antenna mode* and results from the mismatch between antenna impedance and load impedance.

The separation between the antennas is r , which is assumed to be large enough for the tag to be in the far field of the reader. E is the electric field strength of the reader at the tag location. The efficiency of the matching network will be taken as unity and ignored (losses in the network may also be accounted for in the value of G_T). Antenna gains G_R and G_T are expressed relative to an isotropic antenna. From considerations of power flux density at the tag, with λ as the wavelength, we get:

$$P_{Tag} = (E^2 / 120\pi) (\lambda^2 / 4\pi) G_T = V_{Tag}^2 / R_c \quad (3.4)$$

and

$$E^2 / 120\pi = P_R G_R / 4\pi r^2 \quad (3.5)$$

After some manipulation of these equations, we obtain:

$$P_{Tag} = (P_R G_R / 4\pi r^2) (\lambda^2 / 4\pi) G_T = P_R G_R G_T \lambda^2 / (4\pi)^2 r^2 \quad (3.6)$$

The typical maximum reader output power is 500 mW, 2W (ERP, CEPT), and 4W (EIRP, FCC). Converted to dBm, the permitted maximum limits are about 29 dBm (500 mW ERP, 825 mW EIRP), 35 dBm (2W ERP, 3.3W EIRP), and 36 dBm (4W EIRP). The gain of the transmitter (reader) antenna (typical value) is assumed to be 6 dBi. Therefore, the maximum output power from the power amplifier should be 23, 29, and 30 dBm, respectively. The tag available power versus distance can be seen in Figure 5.2. From the industrial experience, the minimum RF input power of 10 μW (20 dBm) to 50 μW (13 dBm) is required to power on the tag. The power received by the tag is then divided in two parts: the reflected power and the available power used by the chip. The distribution of these two parts is very critical for a maximum distance. For dipole antennas presented in the best orientation, GT may be taken as 2 dBi (gain over isotropic with allowance for losses, approximately 1.6).

We can also say that:

$$V_{Tag} = (\lambda/4 \pi r) \sqrt{P_R G_R G_T R_c} \tag{3.7}$$

Note that PRGR is the EIRP of the reader. The maximum practical value of R_c is 600Ω. The received voltage V_{Tag} must be large enough to be rectified and power the tag; a voltage in excess of 1.2 V_{rms} may be required. This is with the tag presented to the interrogating field in the ideal orientation and with no power margin.

Figure 3.2 Tag-received power versus distance.

3.3 Near-Field Propagation Systems

Chapter- 4

4. Design and Simulation of RFID Circuit

The Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) reader consists mainly of a bandpass filter, amplifier, rectifier, lowpass filter and comparator. However, these circuit elements like filters and amplifiers cannot function properly at high frequencies. To address the circuit instability caused by high frequency effects, this paper focuses on designing proper filters and amplifiers by carefully selecting components. Active bandpass filters, active lowpass filters, and amplifiers were implemented by tuning component values to meet RFID reader requirements. Different types and orders of filters were designed and analyzed for the active bandpass and lowpass filters. Frequency response simulations were conducted and verified in NI Multisim to evaluate the filter designs.

Fig. 1 Basic block diagram of RFID system

Over the past several years, RFID (radio frequency identification) devices have been increasingly adopted for a wide range of applications including health monitoring systems, payment systems, access control systems, animal tracking, and other systems aimed at improving security, tracking, and identification.

Fig. 2 Block diagram of RFID reader

RFID tags and readers must be tuned to the same frequency to communicate effectively. RFID systems operate on various frequencies depending on the application. Common frequencies include low frequency (LF) at 125 kHz for short-range, inexpensive applications like security access and asset tracking; high frequency (HF) at 13.56 MHz; ultra-high frequency (UHF) from 850-900 MHz; and microwave at 2.45 GHz for longer range identification. LF systems have the shortest range but are the most affordable option. The performance of filters and amplifiers is crucial for getting the specific signal into the data processing system of RFID readers. The amplifier needs a stable gain when operating at high frequencies. Furthermore, the response curves of bandpass and lowpass filters validate their ability to pass certain frequencies while blocking others.

The block diagram for the RFID reader contains several components that process the signal from the RFID tag. A bandpass filter passes the 125 kHz carrier frequency from the tag while rejecting other frequencies. An amplifier boosts the weak signal to a usable amplitude. A half-wave rectifier eliminates the negative portions of the modulated signal. A lowpass filter removes the 125 kHz carrier frequency but passes the 10 kHz modulation. Finally, a comparator converts the signal back into a stream of digital data. Each component plays a key role in extracting the signal from the tag and converting it into usable digital data for the RFID reader.

4.1 Active Bandpass Filter

Bandpass filters emphasize some frequencies of a signal while attenuating others. The most common circuit designs for bandpass filters are Sallen-Key, multiple feedback, state-variable, and biquad filters. The two most popular bandpass filter topologies are Sallen-Key and multiple feedback designs.

4.1.1 Sallen-Key bandpass design

Design analyses on Sallen-Key bandpass filter have been described by selecting the suitable values of components based on bandpass filter configuration shown in Fig. 3. Firstly, choose C_1 and R_4 for the Sallen-Key bandpass filter and the required values of the components can be calculated by the following equations from (1) to (7).

$$C_2 = \frac{1}{2} C_1 \quad (1)$$

$$R_1 = \frac{2}{k} \quad (2)$$

$$R_2 = \frac{2}{3k} \quad (3)$$

$$R_3 = \frac{4}{k} \quad (4)$$

$$R_5 = \frac{R_4}{(H-1)} \quad (5)$$

$$H = \frac{1}{3} \left(6.5 - \frac{1}{Q} \right) \quad (6)$$

$$k = 2\pi f_o C_1 \quad (7)$$

H = circuit gain in the passband

f_o = cutoff frequency and Q = quality factor

Fig. 3 Sallen-Key bandpass filter

4.1.1 (a) Design Analysis and Simulation Results

The RFID reader circuit is simulated in Multisim using a 1 mV, 125 kHz input signal to represent the output of an RFID tag. For simulation purposes, the 125 kHz carrier signal is modulated with a 10 kHz sine wave, although in practice the modulating signal would be a pulse waveform containing digital data. In Multisim, it is challenging to modulate a sinusoidal carrier with a pulse signal, so using a sinusoidal modulation signal allows system operation to be verified.

To design the bandpass filter, the capacitor C is chosen with different values as shown in Table 1. The capacitor C_2 and resistors R_1 , R_2 , and R_3 are calculated using equations (1) to (7) based on the 125 kHz frequency to achieve the desired bandpass filter response. Based on equation (6), a circuit gain (H) of 2.16 is obtained by selecting a quality factor (Q) of 50, resulting in a sharp magnitude response. However, varying Q does not significantly impact the gain value.

From the equation (5), while choosing $R_1 = 1 \text{ K}\Omega$, R_s has to be $862.1 \text{ }\Omega$ for the circuit gain, $H = 2.16$. Choosing the components values on resistors and capacitors for the filters has to follow the following points:

1. Increasing the capacitance allows to reduce resistance values and therefore the thermal noise.
2. Capacitor with capacitance less of $\sim 100 \text{ pF}$ should be avoided.
3. Reducing the resistance values reduces the thermal noise and therefore the filter noise.
4. Try to use resistor with resistance between few kilo- ohms to few hundreds of kilo-ohms.

From the Fig. 4 (a), 4 (b) and 4 (c) with $C_1 = 1000 \text{ pF}$ (1nF), the frequency of 113.55 kHz can be seen as the center The simulation results conducted in NI Multisim were optimized

to verify that the cutoff frequency of 125 kHz was met. However, the design analysis and simulation results in Table 1 show sharp responses at around 113 kHz with gains of 40.47 dB ($C_1 = 200$ pF), 39.75 dB ($C_1 = 600$ pF), 38.87 dB ($C_1 = 900$ pF), and 34.96 dB ($C_1 = 1000$ pF), as seen in the magnitude response curves. It can be observed that the magnitude response curves at 113 kHz do not satisfy the intended cutoff frequency of 125 kHz and gain of 2.16.

Fig. 4 (a) Sallen-Key bandpass filter with $C_1 = 1$ nF

Fig. 4 (b) Magnitude response at $f_0 = 113.546$ kHz

Fig. 4 (c) Phase response at $f_0 = 113.546$ kHz

Table 1. Design values for Sallen-Key Bandpass filter

C_2	R_1	R_2	R_3	f_0	dB
100 p	12.73 k	4.24 k	25.46 k	113.99 k	40.47
300 p	4.24 k	1.41 k	8.49 k	113.49 k	39.75
450 p	2.83 k	943	5.67 k	113.35 k	38.87
500p	2.55 k	848	5.1 k	113.55 k	34.96

4.1.2 Multiple feedback bandpass design

Although different values of parameters have to be set, these values cannot be tuned to get the sharp response at the cutoff frequency for active bandpass filter on Sallen-Key design. The configuration for multiple feedback bandpass filter has been shown in Fig. 5 [1].

Fig. 5 Multiple feedback bandpass filter

$$f_0 = \frac{1}{2\pi C} \sqrt{\frac{R_1 + R_3}{R_1 R_2 R_3}} \quad (C_1 = C_2 = C) \quad (8)$$

$$A_0 = \frac{R_2}{2R_1} \quad (9)$$

$$R_1 = \frac{Q}{2\pi f_0 C A_0} \quad (10)$$

$$R_2 = \frac{Q}{\pi f_0 C} \quad (11)$$

$$R_3 = \frac{Q}{2\pi f_0 C (2Q^2 - A_0)} \quad (12)$$

f_0 = cutoff frequency, Q = quality factor and A_0 = maximum gain

Components R1 and C1 provides the lowpass responses, and R2 and C2 provide the highpass response. The maximum gain, A_0 , occurs at the center frequency. Q values of less than 10 are typical in this type of filter. The multiple feedback filter uses an op-amp as an integrator and so, the dependence of the transfer function on the op-amp parameters is greater than in the Sallen-Key realization. It is difficult to generate high Q, high frequency sections due to the limitations of the open-loop gain of the op-amp.

4.1.2 (a) Design Analysis and Simulation Results

For the multiple bandpass filters, firstly select the vales of Q and A_0 to get the desired values of the components. Select $Q = 8, 7, 3$ and $A_0 = 3, 1.5$ and 1.1 . The simulation results conducted by NI Multisim have been summarized in Table 2 (a). The desire magnitude responses have not also met the specified frequency of 125 kHz.

Table 2 (a). Design values for multiple feedback filter

A_0	R_1	R_2	R_3	f_0	dB
3	33.95 k	203.72 k	814.87	111.59 k	11.07
1.5	67.91 k	203.72 k	805.21	111.59 k	5.04
1.1	92.6 k	203.72 k	802.67	111.59 k	2.2

Select $A_0 = 1.1$, $C = 100$ pF and $Q = 8, 7, 3$ and 2 as in Table 2 (b). From the simulation results, select $Q = 2$ for the nearest values with the cutoff frequency of 125 kHz.

Table 2 (b). Design values for multiple feedback filter

Q	R_1	R_2	R_3	f_0	dB
8	92.6 k	203.72 k	802.67	111.59 k	2.2
7	81.024 k	178.255 k	919.78	113.5 k	1.9
3	34.72 k	76.39 k	2.26 k	119.38 k	1.08
2	23.15 k	50.93 k	3.69 k	121.41 k	0.96

Select $A_0 = 1.1$, $Q = 2$ and $C = 100$ pF, 800 pF, 900 pF and 1000 pF. The simulation results have been summarized in Table 2 (c). In Fig. 6 (b) and 6 (c), the magnitude curve has a sharp response at the frequency of 121.408 kHz and the phase response shows the degree of 180 and -180 at the frequency of 121.408 kHz which has been chosen to satisfy the requirement of the active bandpass filter. This is reason why the multiple feedback design has been chosen for the bandpass filter with the frequency of 125 kHz.

Table 2 (c). Design values for multiple feedback filter

$C_1 = C_2$	R_1	R_2	R_3	f_0	dB
0.1 nF	23.15 k	50.93 k	3.69 k	121.41 k	0.97
0.5 nF	4.63 k	10.19 k	738	121.41k	0.95
0.9 nF	2.57 k	5.66 k	410.1	121.41 k	0.94

Fig. 6 (a) Multiple feedback bandpass filter

Fig. 6 (b) Magnitude response at $f_0 = 121.408$ kHz

Fig. 6 (c) Phase response at $f_0 = 121.408$ kHz

According to the simulation results, the design values of $C_1 = C_2 = 900$ pF, $R_1 = 2.57$ k Ω , $R_2 = 5.66$ k Ω , $R_3 = 410.1$ k Ω have been optimized for the performance of the bandpass filter in RFID reader.

4.2 Design on Amplifier

The non-inverting amplifier increases the very small signal from the RFID tag to a usable level. In order to ensure for getting the sufficient amount of signal, design consideration of amplifier with larger gain has been described in this paper. The expected gain has to be 1000 for this amplifier. Single stage amplifier with the gain of 1000 has not satisfied with the desired frequency range. Therefore, it needs two stage-amplifier with the total gain of 1000 to meet the desire response. The configuration of the non-inverting amplifier is shown in Fig. 7. The design values of R first stage and $R_2 = 20\text{k}\Omega = 50\text{ K}\Omega$ and $R_{11} = 1\text{ K}\Omega$ for the and $R_{12} = 1\text{ k}$ for the second stage as shown in Fig. 8 have been optimized for the performance of the amplifier in RFID reader. The magnitude curve in Fig. 9 (a) has the gain of about 60 dB till the frequency of about 130.599 kHz. This response curve shows the amplifier gain has been satisfied beyond the cutoff frequency of 125 kHz. The total gain for the two-stage amplifier is A, $51 \times 21 = 1071$ (60.6 dB) which can be calculated by the equation (13) referencing with Fig. 8.

Fig. 7 Non-inverting amplifier configuration

Fig. 8 Bandpass filter and two-stage amplifier

Fig. 9 (a) Magnitude response of two-stage amplifier

Fig. 9 (b) Unity gain bandwidth of two-stage amplifier

Fig. 9 (c) Input and output waveforms of two-stage amplifier

In Fig. 9 (a), it can be observed that the magnitude response of the two-stage amplifier has a wide bandwidth which is worth for the signal with the certain frequency of 125 kHz from bandpass filter. It can be quite clear that the output waveform is amplified by the gain of 1071 in Fig. 9 (c). Also, in Fig. 9 (b), it can be seen that unity gain bandwidth is up to the frequency of 19.192 MHz.

$$A_{cl(NI)} = 1 + \frac{R_f}{R_i} \quad (13)$$

4.3 Active Low Pass Filter

Lowpass filters are used when all low frequencies below the cutoff frequency want to be passed while all high frequencies above the cutoff frequency want to be blocked. In this paper, the rectifier diode before the lowpass filter is used to eliminate the negative portions of the modulated signal from the two-stage amplifier. The lowpass filter in RFID reader rejects the 125 kHz carrier frequency and passes the 10 kHz modulating signal.

Chapter- 5

5. Design Analysis and Simulation Results

Sallen-Key configuration is the suitable design for lowpass filter to get the flat response of passband. Design analyses on Sallen-Key lowpass filter with second order have been described by selecting the suitable values of components shown in Fig.10 [1]. To have the passband for the modulated signal with the cutoff frequency of 10 kHz from rectifier, the component values can be made equal so that $R_A R_B R$ and $C_A C_B = C$. At first, let $C = 10$ nF and the calculated design value of R has been 1.59 K Ω according to the equation (14). The magnitude response curve for the lowpass filter is shown in Fig. 11. The ratio of feedback resistors has to be chosen to get the Butterworth flat response.

Fig. 10 Sallen-Key lowpass filter configuration

$$f_c = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{R_A R_B C_A C_B}} \quad (14)$$

Fig. 11 Magnitude response of 2nd order lowpass filter

From Fig. 11, it needs to provide more roll-off rate and more flat response in the magnitude response for lowpass filter at the certain frequency of 10 kHz. Therefore, the fourth order lowpass filter has been designed to get more flat response and sharp roll-off rate at the critical frequency of 10 kHz as shown in Fig. 13.

Fig. 12 Rectifier and 4th order lowpass filter

Fig. 13 Magnitude response of 4th order lowpass filter

According to the simulation results, the design values of C 10 nF and R = 1.59 ko have been optimized for the performance of the lowpass filter.

5.1 Comparator

A comparator is a specialized op-amp circuit that compares two input voltages and produces an output that is always at either one of two states, indicating the greater or less than relationship between the inputs [1]. In RFID reader, the comparator restores the digital signal to a usable stream of digital data. The comparator of nonzero level detection using voltage-divider reference has been designed to produce the usable level of digital data as shown in Fig. 14.

Fig. 14 Comparator with nonzero level detection

Fig. 15 Comparator with resistive voltage divider values

It can be said that the output of the comparator remains at the maximum negative level as long as the input signal (the output from lowpass filter) into the comparator is less than the reference voltage V_{REF} . When the input voltage exceeds the reference voltage, the output goes to its maximum positive voltage. The input voltage into the comparator is 1.071 V (1 mV x 1071). The reference voltage is calculated by the equation (15) using suitable design values to give the desired output state of the comparator. LM111H is used as the comparator.

$$V_{REF} = \frac{R_2}{R_1 + R_2} (+V) \quad (15)$$

According to the design values of $R_{13} = 20 \text{ k}$ and $R_{14} = 1 \text{ k}$ in Fig. 15, V_{REF} is 0.714 V and the result output waveform of the comparator is shown in Fig. 16.

Fig. 16 Output waveforms of the comparator

5.2 Overall System Simulation Results

In Fig. 17, the first top waveform is the modulated carrier waveform of the amplifier after the bandpass filter. The second top waveform is the resultant output of the rectifier after removing the negative portion of the modulated carrier signal. The third top waveform is the output of the lowpass filter. In this stage, the carrier frequency of 125 kHz has been blocked and the desired signal frequency of 10 kHz has been passed by this lowpass filter. The bottom waveform is the output of the comparator representing the digital data sent to the processor.

Fig. 17 Simulation results of RFID reader

Fig. 18 ASK signal from RFID tag and digital data for reader

5.3 NI Multisim Circuit Simulation

Here's the final NI Multisim simulation's screenshot.

Fig. 19 NI Multisim Simulation Output

Chapter- 6

6. Conclusion

While the circuit devices such as filters and amplifiers operate with increasing frequency, it can be seen that their performance is decreasing. In this paper, for the complete RFID reader system, it is quite evident from the output simulation results that the design values on components of the bandpass and lowpass filter have been satisfied with the requirements of filter characteristics. Also it is clearly observed that design values on components of the amplifier have been satisfied with its stable gain while the frequency is increasing. According to the unity gain bandwidth of 19.192 MHz, the amplifier is capable of producing a voltage gain 1 up to about 19 MHz. Following the rules of thumb, proper selection of components values has been done. Then, the performance of the filters and amplifier has been verified by the magnitude response curves with NI Multisim. As for IC selections, OP 27AH has been chosen in filter designs because of characteristics of low noise, precision operational amplifier. Also AD 845AQ has been selected in the amplifier design for the suitable wide bandwidth and precision. According to the design analyses and simulation results, RFID reader is beneficial for the RFID system. The output digital data of the RFID reader can be applied beneficially into the digital processing system. Fig. 19 shows the complete simulated circuit for RFID reader system.

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